

METHODS OF FILLING THE LEXICAL GAP USING WORD DERIVATION

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Abstract.

This article, proposals and recommendations on the use of words specific to colloquialisms have been developed to fill the lexicon of the literary language. Norms and criteria for the acceptance of word derivative into the lexicon of the literary language have been developed. Methods of identifying gaps in the lexicon of the literary language are described. Considerations for filling them were studied on the example of the Uzbek language, and it was emphasized that the available opportunities should be used effectively. In the development of each language by people and nations, the important aspects of conversational speech are shown. It is proved that the units formed as a result of filling the gaps in the language lexicon in speech situations are stabilized in the lexicon of the literary language.

Keywords.

lexical gap, filling lexical gap, lexical development of the language, word derivative, dialectal words, lexicon of the literary language, stabilization of words at the lexical level.

INTRODUCTION

As any language is realized as a means of creating experiences and thoughts in the thinking of its owners, it develops in a manner appropriate to the development of human thinking. However, the rather limitless nature of thinking and the limitation of language possibilities show that these two objects have a significant disproportion from each other (Majidovich K. A., Filling Lexical Gaps In The Uzbek Language With Dialectisms (Based On The Turkic-Kaltatoy Dialect), 2021).

In the process of speaking, when a person tries to convey his thoughts to the listener, he tries to use all the possibilities of the language (more precisely, his linguistic possibilities). Therefore, when expressing certain concepts, he involuntarily uses existing words in new meanings, creates new words (Hakimova,

2019). Such cases once again prove the great importance of spoken speech in the development of the language.

It is required that the new units that stabilize in the language are first popularized in spoken speech, becoming well-known words for the speakers of the language. For this reason, when filling the lexical gap in the language, first of all, comparing the lexicon of spoken speech with the stable lexical fund of the language and determining a specific lexical gap, thereby filling the relevant lexical gap, is considered a more effective and effective method (Hasanov, 2021).

It should be recognized that although it is not possible to identify the lexical gap, recommend a suitable word for it, and justify it scientifically and practically, as a result of the fair linguistic activity and perception of the language speakers, the lexicon of the language is regularly expanded in an appropriate manner.

Since the main goal of linguistics is to study language phenomena and improve it for human needs, linguists should be leaders and initiators in identifying and filling the lexical gap as soon as possible (Mahmudov, 2017). That is, if the representatives of the field seek to identify and fill the relevant lexical gap through conversational processes or other speech situations, this naturally prepares the ground for the rise of the national and social importance of linguistics.

A systematic study of colloquialisms provides very important information in identifying and filling gaps in the lexicon of the language. In particular, the processes of naming unnamed concepts (or expressing them with other units) can also be observed and seriously studied in conversational speech, and finally, valid conclusions can be drawn.

The process of speaking is a natural form of speech that summarizes other speech situations and conditions, is mixed and, above all, natural. That is why, in filling the lexical space, the language owners are quite active (creative) and initiative, as well as in the position of sorting words (selector and popularizer) to a certain extent (Majidovich K. A., Possibilities of Kipchak Dialects in filling the Lexicon of Uzbek, 2021). This shows that colloquialisms has great potential in spontaneous emergence, sorting and popularization of new words.

Considerable work has been done in Uzbek linguistics regarding the adoption and popularization of word derivative into the literary language. Especially in the works of scientists like Fitrat, V.V.Reshetov, Sh.Shoabdurahmonov, B.Joraev, F.Abdullaev, K.Doniyorov, A.Hojiev, A.Ishaev, R.Jomonov, N.Murodova, the literary language lexicon of word derivative Considerable opinions were expressed about the possibilities of enrichment. In recent years, scientists such as N.

Mahmudov, Z. Kholmanova, A. Madvaliev, Y. Odilov have carried out significant work on the analysis of changes in the lexicon of the literary language.

METHODS

First, we will see how to find the lexical gap in representative examples. In this, it is aimed to observe the speech-specific units and find the corresponding lexical space (Ҳасанов А. , Ўзбек адабий тилидаги лексик лакуналарнинг диалектал асослари, 2021). For example, by comparing lexical systems of limited use with the lexicon of a literary language, many units that are lexical gaps for a literary language can be identified. There are following types of this method:

a) spaces observed in the comparison of literary language and word derivative: Ø - birrovchilar, Ø - soqqa ;

b) gaps observed in the comparison of literary language and dialect words: Ø - luk (egg in a bowl), Ø - sargāli (yellow cherry);

v) lexical gaps observed in the comparison of literary language and professionalisms: Ø - shushang (shears for shearing the wool of sheep and goats);

g) lexical spaces observed in the comparison of literary language and barbarisms: Ø - okey, Ø - nu;

d) lexical spaces observed in the comparison of literary language and slangs: Ø - to open, Ø - to sleep.

e) gaps observed in the comparison of literary language and slang: Ø - xorak ("alien" victim); Ø - atomri (in the sense of "continue your work");

or) gaps observed in the comparison of literary language and jargon: Ø - niche, Ø - to justify;

determined by this method are of great importance in terms of the presence of a complementary unit in the microsystem selected for comparison (Tashmatova, 2022). The use of units from the lexical system under comparison in filling these lexical gaps serves to a certain extent the rapid popularization of these units in live speech. Therefore, it is effective to pay attention to these possibilities when identifying and filling lexical gaps in the language.

It is necessary to follow certain criteria when filling identified lexical gaps. Completing the literary language on the basis of internal capabilities as an effective method of enriching the language lexicon serves to preserve the purity of the language and improve its expressive possibilities. Naming the concepts that appear in the mind as a result of the consistent development of thinking on the basis of the internal capabilities of the language must necessarily follow certain standards and criteria (Majidovich K. A., Filling Lexical Gaps In The Uzbek Language With Dialectisms (Based On The Turkic-Kaltatoy Dialect), 2021). It is noted in most

literature that the literary language has standardized and stable aspects by its nature. This requires paying special attention to the following aspects when filling the gaps in the lexicon of the literary language:

1. The concept evaluated as a lexical gap in the literary language should be socially and linguistically important. This aspect also serves to describe the urgency of filling the lexical gap.

Try to evaluate and fill in the lexical gap concepts that are not important enough for language owners, as well as those that are used in a narrow field and are rarely referred to in speech. In particular, the literary word *killik* (a device that shears the wool of sheep and goats), which is used only in the process of shearing in cattle breeding, does not have such great social significance (Umurzakova, 2020). Although this concept represents a specific working tool, it is not necessarily relevant for all language speakers.

The fact that the concept planned to be named in the AT is important for the daily life and activities of the speakers of the language, increases the necessity and possibility of its naming. This is crucial in naming the concept.

2. When filling the lexical gaps in the literary language, it is good to analyze the units identified by comparing the lexicon of the literary language with colloquialisms and dialectal words (Хасанов А. М., 2021). As a result of comparative studies, it is easier to describe the appropriateness of the relevant lexical space by justifying the relevance and importance of the concepts expressed by these words than to give a literary name to a concept that does not have its own representative.

This criterion is also of great importance in the positive introduction of filling the lexical gap in the literary language.

3. The word recommended to fill the lexical gap in the literary language should be able to incorporate most of the important features of the literary language units. In other words, a new word introduced into the lexical system should be a word that quickly adapts to this system, shows the characteristics of similar units, and can enter into a lexical-grammatical relationship with other units (Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language (O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati), 2020). It is difficult for a word that cannot embody these characteristics to be stabilized in the lexicon of the literary language.

At this point, it should be noted that the lexicon of the literary language, which forms the main vocabulary of the language, includes the most necessary elements for social life and everyday life, which have been used in the language for many periods, are actively used in the process of communication, are

understandable to the public, and also create other new words and word forms. important words that can be the basis for doing are introduced (Toshnazarovna). In other words, its linguistic significance is also very important in raising a word to the level of a literary language unit, in taking a place in the main vocabulary. Linguistic importance is defined as the ability of a word to form new words and word forms, to manifest categorical features in lexical and grammatical relations.

4. The new word recommended to fill the lexical gap in the literary language should be easy to use, understandable for most speakers, widely popular, and most importantly, it should be a word created based on the internal capabilities of the Uzbek language (БЫКОВА, 2003). In this regard, giving special preference to the words used in the old Uzbek language (or Turkish language), which are still used in conversation or in some dialects, is a very correct way (Togayev, 2020). This also serves to preserve the national image, purity and nationalism of the language.

Shuvat used in different regions of Uzbekistan. The verb shivalamaq related to this word is also actively used in conversation. At the same time, it is unique to the Turkic language and is one of the words found in related languages. The word shuvat means "rain falling in the form of small particles (not drops!)". The inclusion of such words in the dictionaries of the literary language is also of great importance in the naming of the corresponding concept.

5. A new literary term should not be included in the lexicon of a literary language when a suitable (alternative) word exists in the literary language for the concept evaluated as a lexical gap, and when it is acceptable to use a word with a similar meaning in its expression (Rakhimjonovich, 2020). For example, the word (Xolmanova, 2015) kuzatmoq to express the concept of "to go somewhere together to say goodbye to someone who is leaving, to go somewhere and leave and say goodbye". In fact, this word, which has the meaning of "to look carefully for the purpose of knowing, to determine, to examine", is characterized by the expression of the above concept on the basis of a certain similarity and connection (Хасанов А. М., 2021). And it is not a secret to anyone that the word kuzatmoq name that concept. This shows that the corresponding concept is not a gap for the lexicon of the language and there is no need to fill it.

6. It is appropriate to use the internal capabilities of the language when naming new concepts that have entered from other cultures (Хасанов А. , ON THE DIFFERENCES BETWEEN LITERARY AND DIALECTAL VOCABULARY, 2020). However, if this concept has entered the language under its own name and is widely popular in conversation, then it is not justified to insert a new word instead of that word (Majidovich K. A., Possibilities of Kipchak Dialects in filling the

Lexicon of Uzbek, 2021). Because in most cases such cases do not end with the expected result. The ineffectiveness of some initiatives to make our language pure Uzbek at the end of the last century also confirms the above points.

However, it is worth noting that the concept coming from a foreign culture is very early, that is, if it is popularized and popularized with an Uzbek name as soon as it is introduced, it can settle in the lexicon of the language.

As some scientists have rightly pointed out, in order to express new things and phenomena that appear in life (on a global scale), a new word is created based on the capabilities of the language or a word representing this thing or concept is adopted in another language. In such changes that occur during the gradual development of the language, it is of great importance for the purity and immortality of the language that the people of the nation behave rationally and fairly and follow the necessary standards and criteria in the process of acquiring words.

Should be more convenient and possible than other lexical units (or borrowings) that are equivalent to it. In the common language, the word *tayishmaq*, which names an injury expressed by a few words, such as "stretching a leg", "musculi lat emok", is a suitable word for the corresponding lexical space in the literary language. This word is distinguished by its ease compared to other equivalents: the relevant concept is represented by one (whole) word (Majidovich K. A., 2021). This ensures its superiority over other options and privileges its introduction into the literary language. Of course, in this process, which word will be stabilized among the alternative options will acquire a probable character. In other words, the selection of language units as a standard among options is both a historical and a spontaneous process, and their use or rejection is at the discretion of the people who are the creators and consumers of the language. However, when recommending them individually, it is necessary to pay attention to the aspects of convenience.

RESULTS

Word derivative are distinguished by their colorfulness, natural construction and active use. Linguistic meaning also finds its meaning in these words. Because cases such as euphemism and taboo are, in fact, units that show the specific linguistic manners of the speakers.

Words like *uloqlamoq*, *buzoqlamoq*, which are based on the productive word formation patterns of the Uzbek language, are among the words that have a noticeable euphemism. The active use of these words in rural areas engaged in animal husbandry requires that they be recorded in literary language dictionaries

(Majidovich K. A., USE OF METAPHORICAL WORD FORMATION IN FILLING LEXICAL GAPS IN THE LANGUAGE., 2022).

Some words are unique to speech and become one of the most actively used units in the speech of representatives of the relevant field. One such word is the word *yiloshi*. This word is used by an employee performing his duties as a means of communicating his work and authority to another person.

In our opinion, such nationally characterized words must be included in dictionaries and described.

The gender differentiation and comparative expression of human characteristics is clearly reflected in such words as *xotinmijoz*, *xotinchalish*, *erkakshoda*. Among these words, the word has the right to be included in dictionaries as one of the words actively used in conversational processes. Because it is a more stable unit today as a worthy representative of the concept it represents (Sankaravelayuthan, 2020).

The word *khokimak*, which is used in many regions, is also one of the words that are actively used in speech. The word *koqim*, which is used in a similar way to this word, is also derived from this verb. This word, which is an element of the Turkic language, has the meaning of "contaminating a house or a place with various things, waste, disordering". In our opinion, such words should be included in dictionaries without exception.

One of the word derivative, *khokakhorsin*, means "done only for the satisfaction and satisfaction of the leader and chief." The syntactical construction of this word and its many uses make it easy to understand (Adamska-Salaciak, 2021). These aspects also contribute to the stability of this word as a linguistic unit.

Carrying the purchased products in the market and supermarkets and buying the next product is a huge inconvenience for the customer. The wheelchair used in this process is attached to the person in this place. This vehicle, which is unusual to name in the form of a cart or basket, is colloquially called a cart style. This tool can also be applied to a cart that pulls a carrier (loader) in large markets. It is not difficult to notice that the suffix *-cha* is not only a means of diminution in this word, but also serves to distinguish similar types of the word to which it is added from each other. In our opinion, the word *buggy* should also be included in dictionaries as a separate word.

The word *flesh-and-nail* is used to express the inseparable, integral, interdependence of two people (or things) close to each other. In fact, the fact that the same concept is a lexical gap in the language, which is a product of the simile "like flesh and nails", loaded with the meanings of "even if there are two, closely

related to each other, integral, one cannot be without the other", gives the possibility to stabilize this word as a literary language unit.

Sotarman, olarman speech, there are words that are significantly different from other constructions due to the characteristic of this style of formation. Because there are not many words related to the suffix -man in the lexicon of the literary language, and they are mainly formed from the literaryization of word derivative (Quan-zhi, 2017). Even today, the above words made with the help of this suffix have the opportunity to become literary with their active use and the possibilities of naming the relevant lexical space. The word erghman, made with the same suffix, is used in the sense of "a divorced or deceased woman who joins her and goes to another (accepting) family." It is not difficult to notice that dysephemism is strong in this word, both from the explanation and from the basis of construction. This word, applied to a child who has a bad fate, can be interpreted as a message to his parents that the child should not be separated from his family. It is permissible to include this word in the dictionary as one of the words that are actively used in conversation.

It is not a secret to anyone that another colloquial word, o'la-o'lguncha. In this word, which is formed from the repetition of a base, it is possible to notice that the phenomenon of death (dying) is slightly veiled (Khasanov, 2020). This word appeared due to the habit, increased level of activity, characteristic of the speech of some older people and women. In our opinion, this word should also be included in the explanatory dictionary.

The conjugation of the name of the action is actively used today in the naming of many lexical spaces. One such word is the word constraint. This word is widely used in colloquial speech in the sense of limitation and reduction of certain rights and freedoms. The same features are also undergoing processes of consolidation in the causal language. This makes it possible for it to be included in the dictionaries of the literary language.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

It is doubtful whether all the words analyzed above can be included in the lexicon of the literary language. In other words, the implementation of these works is spontaneous. Among them, many words are suitable to reach the level of a literary language unit. And some are not. "In general, from the point of view of the process of enrichment of the literary language at the expense of the dialectal and colloquial lexicon, words related to the dialectal and colloquial language can be divided into the following three layers: 1) words that remain unique to dialects and colloquial language (for example, innaykin, (followed by the literary language), ja

(very in literary language)); 2) words in the process of transition to literary language; 3) words transferred to the literary language (Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language (O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati), 2020). The first category of words in this classification does not deserve to be literary (Ҳасанов А. , 2022). The third category is literary words. Therefore, the second category intermediate between these two categories, i.e. the words in the process of transition to the literary language (which can be transferred), can be evaluated as a lacunar unit for the literary language. However, it is not easy to determine their fate of becoming literate or "forgotten".

In general, according to lexicographic criteria "from colloquial and dialectal words, the following are included in the dictionary:

a) words that are widely used in conversation and are often found in written literature: zap, rosa, paqqos, unaka, shunangangi, boplamoq, kotirmoq ;

b) synonymous words used in parallel in the literary language: narvon – shoti, so'ri – karovat – chorpoya etc.;

c) words that are not recorded in written literature, but do not have a parallel in the literary language (alternatively - A.H): elvizak, aydin, chaptar, so'g'on and so on;

g) words found in written literature (tetoya, atak-chechak, etc.) that are unique to certain places and have no parallel in the literary language: negov, qaqas (Fergana), kamgak (Tashkent), and so on. Clauses "c" and "g" of this classification directly refer to words that are lacunar units for literary language. In fact, it was recognized very early that words of this type fill the gaps in the literary language and thereby increase the expressive potential of the language. However, the lexicographical experiments in the literaryization of such words are not worthy of praise. On the contrary, the initiative of wordsmiths and mass media in the literaryization of these types of words was more effective than that of lexicographers and linguists. However, in this regard, there are enough dialectological sources and experiences in national linguistics.

Considerable progress has been made in Uzbek linguistics. But this is still not enough for science. In recent years, it should be noted that the anthropocentric paradigm, which is mainly based on the study of language together with its creator - the human factor, is gaining more priority in research in the field of linguistics. As a result, many features and practical possibilities of the language are being developed. At the same time, the most important issue of linguistics, i.e. attempts to systematize language purity and lexical development, is allowed to be admitted that nowadays it has weakened considerably (Mahmudov, 2017). After all, the

consistent development of any language requires the re-study and improvement of existing scientific and theoretical sources and foundations. Based on this need, one of the important tasks of Uzbek linguistics today is to fill the lexical gaps in the current Uzbek literary language, to introduce words from dialects and colloquial speech into the literary language, and to enrich the lexicon of the language on this basis.

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